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D.2.2 E-RIHS Quality Manual and KPIs

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Abstract

The future **E-RIHS ERIC** was designed to have **Quality** as one of its **main pillars**. To ensure its high level throughout the partnership, quality criteria must be met by all organizations and research groups that may state a connection with E-RIHS.

The deliverable describes the **quality system** proposed to be adopted by E-RIHS for the quality assessment of prospective new partners and their services and for the quality audit of existing E-RIHS partners and their services. It also outlines the process to grant external organizations, services, projects and proposals the affiliation to E-RIHS, or its support. All such procedures are based on a modular operation: the evaluation of the candidate's internal processes, of its scientific excellence and of the quality of its services and eventual suitability for E-RIHS.

The deliverable is organized in separate documents appended to the main document which includes the principles of quality assessment. The appended documents treat the assessment methodology of technical resources and digital contributions to the common database, a basic quality manual for its partners, a common KPI system, and guidelines on Ethics to be implemented throughout the partnership.

The deliverable constitutes a fundamental contribution for the design of the future ERIC. It was written by the E-RIHS PP Task 2.3 *Quality systems and KPIs* leader in cooperation with colleagues and made available for over 90 days before submission in the Project site on D4Science for comments by all E-RIHS PP partners.

DISCLAIMER:

This document reflects the state of advancement of the preparatory work at the time of its delivery. As such, its content may be subject to further evolution.

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Abstract (for dissemination)	The deliverable describes the quality system proposed to be adopted by E-RIHS for the quality assessment of prospective new partners and their services and for the quality audit of existing E-RIHS partners and their services.
Keywords	E-RIHS: Heritage Science; Quality System; Quality Manual; KPI.

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Abbreviations

BSD – Berkeley Software Distribution.

CC-NC license – Creative Commons – Non-Commercial license.

CC0 – CC0 1.0 Universal (Creative Commons deed with no-copyright dedication).

DIGILAB – The repository of externally accessible data of E-RIHS.

DIN – Deutsches Institut für Normung (German Standardization Institute).

DMP – Data Management Plan.

DSA - Data Seal of Approval (a self-assessment process for digital archives, aimed at archives that hold data).

EOSC - European Open Science Cloud.

ERIC – European Research Infrastructure Consortium.

E-RIHS – European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science

EU – European Union.

FAIR - Data which meet standards of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability.

GPL – General Public Licence.

HS – Heritage Science.

IEC – International Electrotechnical Commission.

ISO - International Organization for Standardization.

KER - Key Evaluator Ratings (average of scores attributed by a team of evaluators appointed by the E-RIHS management on a scale of 1 – poor - to 10 – excellent - corresponding to a quantification of subjective appraisals of the quality level of the feature examined).

KPI - Key Performance Indicators (values that may be objectively measured allowing an unbiased appraisal of operational effectiveness).

NC – Non-Commercial.

OAI-PMH - Open Archives Initiative - Protocol for Metadata Harvesting.

QBoard – Quality Board (a permanent group within E-RIHS responsible for performing the quality assessment procedures).

QManager – E-RIHS Quality Manager.

RG – Research Group (any individualized group of researchers and technical support active in the context of E-RIHS).

Narrative (technical) description

The purpose of Task 2.3 is to develop a quality system, applying the principles and options of quality management, appropriate for E-RIHS and including its various activities, aimed at allowing all parties to have confidence in the results obtained and initiatives organized under the E-RIHS umbrella. “Confidence in the results” is understood as referring to the organizational, personal and instrumental contributions to operational outcomes. A list of Key Performance Indicators was also to be proposed within this Task.

For the sake of flexibility, the deliverable is constituted by a main document called “E-RIHS Quality Policy” including the principles of quality management within E-RIHS and a number of appended separate documents dealing with particular aspects of quality assurance and assessment: *Qualitative Performance Indicators; Evaluation of data provision services and datasets for DIGILAB; KPIs for the self-assessment and periodic assessment of partners; E-RIHS Quality Manual guidance document; and E-RIHS policy on Ethics.*

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